

ANALYSIS OF SENSORY PROPERTIES, CHEMICAL PROPERTIES, TEXTURE, CHEWINESS AND COLOR OF PEMPEK MADE FROM PARANG-PARANG FISH (*Chirocentrus dorab*) AND SNAPPER FISH (*Lutjanus spp*) WITH THE ADDITION OF SOY PROTEIN ISOLATE

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Abstract

Pempek is a traditional Palembang Indonesia food made from a mixture of fish and tapioca flour, then processed by boiling and frying before being served with cuko pempek sauce. Generally, the types of fish used in making pempek are mackerel, belida, or cork due to their high protein content and chewy and elastic texture (Yuliana et al., 2021). Limited sources of these fish, increasing prices, and seasonal factors, encourage the need for alternative fish ingredients that are more sustainable, economical, and easily obtained. This study aims to analyze the sensory, chemical and physical properties of pempek made from parang-parang and snapper fish with the addition of soy protein isolate. The addition of soy protein isolate (SPI) has been shown to improve texture, increase bound water content and emulsion stability in meat and fish-based products (Tang et al, 2020). SPI can also improve the elasticity and water binding capacity of surimi products (Wang et al, 2019). The treatments applied were parang-parang and snapper fish with the addition of 0%, 2%, 4% and 6% SPI. Parameters measured were sensory properties, protein content, water content, chewiness and brightness of the pempek produced. Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to see the effect of treatment on the parameters measured. The results showed that the addition of SPI in making pempek made from parang paarang fish and snapper fish had a significant effect on elasticity, moisture content and protein content, but no significant effect on sensory properties and color brightness.

INTRODUCTION

Pempek is a traditional Palembang food made from a mixture of fish and tapioca flour, then processed by boiling and frying before being served with cuko pempek sauce. Generally, the types of fish used in making pempek are mackerel, belida, or cork due to their high protein content and chewy and elastic texture. However, the limitations of these fish sources, the increasing price, and seasonal factors, encourage the need for alternative fish ingredients that are more sustainable, economical, and easy to obtain.

Parang-parang fish (*Chirocentrus dorab*) and snapper fish (*Lutjanus spp.*) are known as marine fish that have high protein content and good essential amino acid content, so they can be used as an alternative in making pempek. A study by Nurhayati et al. (2022) showed that marine fish meat has the potential to produce processed fish products with functional quality and competitive nutritional value compared to freshwater fish. However, the unique physicochemical and flavor characteristics of both types of fish may affect the sensory properties and final texture of pempek products.

The addition of protein stabilizers such as soy protein isolate (SPI) has been shown to improve texture, increase bound water content and emulsion stability in various processed food products, including meat- and fish-based products (Tang et al., 2020). SPI also helps to increase

the nutritional value of pempek by adding certain amino acids that may be lacking in fish. A study by Wang et al. (2019) found that the addition of SPI in surimi products increased elasticity and water holding capacity, and improved color appearance and taste.

METHODOLOGY

Methods and Materials

This study used the experimental method (completely randomized design, with two main factors: fish species (parang-parang fish and snapper fish) and soy protein isolate concentration (0%, 2%, 4%, and 6%). Each treatment combination was replicated three times. To see the effect of treatment on the measured parameters, analysis of variance (ANOVA) is used. The parameters measured include consumer preference sensory tests, water content, protein content, elasticity, hardness and color brightness. The parameters measured include consumer preference sensory tests by 30 semi-trained panelists, water content, protein content, elasticity, hardness and color brightness. The hedonic scale used is 1 (very dislike), 2 (dislike), 3 (quite dislike), 4 (slightly like), 5 (normal), 6 (slightly like), 7 (quite like), 8 (like), 9 (very like)

The materials used were fresh parang-parang (*Chirocentrus dorab*) and red snapper (*Lutjanus campechanus*), tapioca flour, salt, and water, SPI, analytical chemicals (NaOH, HCl, phenolphthalein, etc.).

The equipment used were Ohaus Pioneer PA214 digital scales for weighing, Philips HR2221/00 blender for pulverizing fish meat, KitchenAid 5KPM5 mixer for homogenizing the dough, AND MX 50 moisture analyzer for analyzing moisture content, shiomadzu UV-1800 UV-Vis spectrophotometer for protein analysis, Stable Micro Systems TA. XT Plus for measure strength and suppleness, Minolta CR-400 colorimeter for measure color,

How to make pempek

- 1) Fish meat is separated from bones and skin and dirt then finely chopped.
- 2) Fish meat is then pulverized with a blender
- 3) Soya protein isolate was added according to the treatment (0%, 2%, 4%, 6%) and stirred until homogeneous.
- 4) Add water 50% of the amount of fish (V/W), salt (how many grams). Stir until it almost forms a gel.
- 5) Add tapioca amount of fish (W/W). Mix until smooth
- 6) Shape the dough into a lenjer shape, then boil in boiling water until it floats.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Sensory Properties

The addition of SPI increased the total sensory score up to 4% concentration, but decreased slightly at 6% concentration. This indicates that the addition of SPI to a certain extent can improve the texture, flavor and chewiness of pempek, but excessive addition can decrease palatability. Sensory scores showed that snapper fish was slightly preferred over parang-parang fish at almost all SPI concentrations. This could be related to the basic flavor of the fish and the texture of the meat (Fig.1).

Fig 1: The Sensory Properties of Pempek Made from *Chirocentrus dorab* and *Lutjanus sp* With the Addition SPI

2. Water Content (%)

The moisture content of pempek from parang-parang and snapper fish showed a decreasing trend as the concentration of soy protein isolate (SPI) increased. This can be explained because the addition of SPI increases the water binding ability of the dough, so that more water is bound and not measured as free water content.

SPI contains proteins with high hydrophilic properties, so it can bind water in the food system (Sathe et al., 1982). The difference in fish species did not seem to significantly affect the moisture content, although snapper tended to have a slightly higher moisture content at 0% SPI concentration (Fig.2).

Fig 2: The Water Content of Pempek Made from *Chirocentru dorab* and *Lutjanus sp* with The Addition SPI

3. Protein Content (%)

Increasing the SPI concentration from 0% to 6% led to an increase in the protein content of pempek, both for parang-parang and snapper. SPI is a pure vegetable protein source with a protein content of more than 90% (Kinsella, 1979). Therefore, the addition of SPI directly increases the total protein content of the product. Snapper showed slightly higher protein content than parang-parang fish at each SPI concentration level, possibly due to differences in the initial protein composition of the two fish species (Fig.3).

Fig 3: The Protein Content of Pempek Made from Chirocentrus and Lutjanus sp With The Addition SPI

4. Chewiness Level

The figure above shows the chewiness level of pempek made from two types of fish, Chirocentrus dorab (parang-parang fish) and Lutjanus spp (snapper fish), with the addition of isolated soy protein (SPI - Isolated Soy Protein) at concentrations of 0%, 2%, 4%, and 6% (Fig.4).

It can be seen that the higher the concentration of SPI added, the higher the level of chewiness of the pempek produced, both in pempek made from Chirocentrus dorab and Lutjanus spp. This indicates a positive correlation between the addition of SPI and the increase in chewiness.

Zhang et al. (2009) in the Journal of Food Engineering stated that the addition of SPI in meat or fish-based products can increase chewiness because soy protein strengthens the protein network through gel formation and reticulation between molecules.

This is also in accordance with the statement of Astawan (2004) who explained that the use of soy protein isolates in the food industry, including in fish-based products, can improve nutritional value as well as physical characteristics such as chewiness and texture density, making it a very useful functional additive.

Fig 4: The Chewiness Level of Pempek Made from Chirocentrus dorab fish and Lutjanus sp with the Addition SPI

Pempek from Chirocentrus dorab consistently showed higher chewiness than Lutjanus spp at every level of SPI addition. This could indicate that the protein composition and natural texture of Chirocentrus dorab favored the formation of a chewy gel network when combined with SPI. The addition of SPI increases the water holding capacity and gel formation of protein-based products, resulting in a denser and chewier texture. SPI can also improve the interaction between protein molecules during the heating process, which contributes to the final texture of processed fish products such as pempek.

5. Hardness

It can be seen that the higher the addition of SPI, the hardness of the pempek tends to decrease for both types of fish. This indicates that SPI has an effect in softening the texture or reducing the hardness of the product. Wang et al. (2001) in the Journal of Food Science explained that soy protein isolate has the ability to improve the texture of meat and fish products by binding water and increasing viscoelasticity, which can reduce product hardness.

Fig 5: The Hardness of Pempek Made from Chirocentrus dorab and Lutjanus sp with the Addition SPI

Pempek made from *Chirocentrus dorab* consistently showed higher hardness than *Lutjanus* spp. This difference may be due to differences in protein characteristics between fish species, especially collagen content and gelling ability. The decrease in hardness as SPI increases is likely due to the functional properties of SPI in increasing water retention and forming a more flexible and elastic protein network. SPI can also reduce protein bonds that are too dense or hard, resulting in a more tender texture (Fig.5).

6. Color L* Value (Light-Dark)

The L* value increased with the addition of SPI in both types of fish, indicating a lighter product color. This is due to the off-white nature of SPI, so its addition causes the pempek batter to become brighter (Hettiarachchy et al., 1996). Snapper consistently showed slightly higher L* values than parang-parang. It can be seen that as more SPI is added, the brightness (white degree) of the pempek increases for both types of fish (Fig.6). This indicates that

Fig 6: The Color L* Value (whitene Degreee) of Pempek Made from Chirocentrus dorab and Lutjanus sp with the addition SPI

the addition of SPI has a positive effect on the light color of the final product. Pempek from *Lutjanus* spp showed higher white degree values than *Chirocentrus dorab* at all levels of SPI addition. This could be related to the initial flesh color of the fish: snapper generally has lighter flesh than parang-parang. SPI has an off-white to light beige color, so when mixed in products such as pempek, it can improve the appearance of the product color to be brighter. SPI can also reduce the intensity of dark colors derived from myoglobin components or other pigments in fish.

Chang & Ng (2005) in the Journal of Food Science stated that soy protein isolate has a neutral to light color, so its use in food products can increase the brightness and whiteness (white degree) of processed products.

It can be seen that the a* value decreases gradually as the addition of SPI increases in both fish species. This indicates that the intensity of the reddish color in the pempek products decreased when higher amounts of SPI were added.

According to Trout (1989) in the Journal of Food Science, the addition of soy protein isolate decreases the a^* value in processed meat products because natural color pigments such as myoglobin become less dominant due to pigment dilution and changes in the protein environment. Similarly, Lawrie & Ledward (2006) in Lawrie's Meat Science explained that a^* value is strongly influenced by pigment content (such as myoglobin) and pH. The addition of ingredients such as SPIs that can alter protein structure and local pH can affect red color stability. Pempek from *Chirocentrus dorab* fish showed higher a^* values than *Lutjanus spp* at all SPI levels. This could be due to the natural color characteristics of *Chirocentrus dorab* fish meat which has higher red pigments or is more active in the processing reaction. SPI generally has an off-white color, so the mixing effect tends to dilute the natural color of the main raw material.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The addition of SPI up to 4% concentration was able to increase the total sensory score.
- 2) The moisture content of pempek from parang-parang and kakap fish showed a decreasing trend as the concentration of soy protein isolate (SPI) increased.
- 3) Increasing the concentration of SPI from 0% to 6% caused an increase in protein content in pempek, both parang-parang and snapper fish.
- 4) It can be seen that the higher the concentration of SPI added, the higher the level of chewiness of the pempek produced, both in pempek made from *Chirocentrus dorab* and *Lutjanus spp*.
- 5) The L^* value increases with the addition of SPI in both fish species, indicating a lighter color of the product.
- 6) It can be seen that the a^* value decreases gradually as the addition of SPI in both fish species increases. This indicates that the intensity of the reddish color of the pempek product decreases when higher amounts of SPI are added.

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